

INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHER

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Saidova Valida

*3rd year student of the Faculty of Philology
of the Uzbekistan State University of World Languages*

Abstract: *The article describes the development of family, community and school cooperation in the formation of creative activity in primary school students, the motivational components of the structure of innovative activity, the issues of creativity in the innovative activity of the teacher*

Keywords: *class, school, methodical, innovative, element, profession, motive, creativity*

Аннотация: *В статье рассматриваются вопросы развития сотрудничества семьи, сообщества и школы в формировании творческой активности младших школьников, мотивационные компоненты структуры инновационной деятельности, вопросы творчества в инновационной деятельности учителя.*

Ключевые слова: *класс, школа, методический, новаторский, элемент, профессия, мотив, творчество.*

INTRODUCTION

In the education system of the Republic, the issue of forming creative activity in primary school students is considered as an opportunity for members of society to think independently, to express their views and opinions. In this regard, the Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that

“ increase activity”

That is why the development of family, community and school cooperation in the formation of creative activity in primary school students, the creation of a didactic system of early detection of creative abilities in primary school students, theoretical and methodological substantiation and application of methods of organizing creative activities it is important to determine the didactic conditions of the oriented pedagogical process.

RESEARCH METHODS

The motivational component of the structure of innovative activity plays an important role in the innovative activity of the teacher.

Innovative activity is an external incentive (financial reward, high rank, the need for service, etc.), the motivation of the teacher to external self-esteem or the pursuit of prestige, professional motivation (study and

upbringing). desire, learners' focus on innovation, etc.), occurs under the influence of self-fulfillment motives. The innovative activity of the teacher is consistently built on the obvious advantage of one of the listed motives as follows:

1. External incentives related to material rewards for certain elements of innovation. Such incentives may include rewards, incentives, satisfactory working conditions and procedures, requirements and controls for participation in higher-level competitions, in particular the Teacher of the Year competition. In this case, the teacher's work is directly related to the results of professional activity. The peculiarity of the teacher's work with external motivation in achieving the goal by various means is that he performs the necessary and sufficient amount of work from a formal point of view. He focuses on the external aspects of his work. There is almost no effort to improve skills, with the exception of studying in isolation from school work, without losses in the field of financial incentives and significant changes in working conditions, it is easy to change jobs.

2. Motives of teacher self-assertion (self-assertion through external positive evaluations of others). In this case, the teacher is engaged in introducing innovations into his or her work for a social purpose. This motive can be called a motive of prestige.

3. Professional motive. The psychological nature of the two motives discussed above is primarily related to the satisfaction of non-professional needs, and in the second - the goal associated with the motive of self-emphasis, to increase self-esteem. 'lib serves, which is a necessary condition of a person's comfortable psychological state. Professional motivation serves as a more general desire to teach and nurture children.

4. Motives for personal self-realization. According to a number of researchers, the need for self-activation, which consists of a person's desire to "be what he can be," is potentially present in all people, but also in everyone's professional activities. and especially not consciously manifested.

The next component of the structure is creativity (the ability to create their own new ideas, to abandon the traditional scheme of thinking, to quickly solve problem situations, etc.). In foreign pedagogical theory, pedagogical creativity is replaced by the concept of creativity.

Many researchers associate the concepts of creativity and innovation as perceptions of innovation and openness to innovation when the need for change is felt.

Creativity is an important characteristic of a teacher's innovative activity. In national psychology, creativity depends on the ability to express socially significant creative activity", the creative potential of man is considered as a certain feature of the human individual (stable feature).

The development of creativity is greatly influenced by the individual characteristics of the individual, his emotional and motivational factors. Personal qualities that distinguish creative people from non-creative ones are self-confidence, aggression, self-satisfaction, social limitations, and non-acceptance of strangers

'opinions.

The study of creativity is widely represented in the national science. Criteria for creativity have been identified, and its psychological mechanisms are being actively studied.

A set of didactic tools provided to young students based on a traditional educational process based on knowledge. They come in the form of curricula, textbooks, study guides. As a reworked form of culture, learning materials are provided to students as part of the curriculum.

The subject area reflects the knowledge, skills and competencies required in the STS. Students can form ideas in relation to material beings. A person develops his thoughts independently, he is not ready to master them. Thoughts are formed through aspirations, experiences, and emotions, which are formed through the use of productive methods. Materials that allow information to be shared and collaborated directly also help students to form an objective opinion. External demands that are not based on values and independent thinking mechanisms do not serve to expand students' creative thinking abilities.

Only personal thinking can help students develop creative skills. Personality formation is a process of socially dependent self-development. It represents the inner aspiration of the student from low to high level of development. In such a situation, external causes move through internal conditions. Under the same conditions, creative activity is observed in a particular student. In another group of students, this is not the case. In this process, the student's attitude towards learning activities is important. The question of what this relationship looks like can be answered in an active, passive, or indifferent way.

CONCLUSION

In the same way, it is possible to predict the development prospects of creative activity in students. The development of such activity takes place through the control of various manifestations of reflection. They are action-based, subjective, and personal. Psychological mechanisms of action-based and subjective manifestations of reflection The action-based and content-based parts of creative activity show imbalances between a person's new needs and knowledge, skills, and abilities.

Personal reflexes are formed as a result of the elimination of previous contradictions about reading, overcoming the contradictions of the

individual's worldview and emotional state. The emergence of creative activity in students requires the acquisition of knowledge to develop its specific parts. Examples include inclinations, worldviews, emotional-voluntary, meaningful-action, and reflexive parts. Their interactions and interrelationships are manifested as a set of harmonized units. It should be borne in mind that the habit, which is characteristic of each person, has its own rhythm and conditions of development. One of the characteristics is to determine the level of development of the parts of students' creative activities. This approach allows students to choose the tools that will develop their creative skills in a purposeful way, helping them to focus their creative energy on a specific goal. Accordingly, it is possible to distinguish 3 levels of development of creative activity skills in students. They are low level, medium level and high level. As a result of modeling such a system, it is possible to ensure the didactic consistency of individual pedagogical situations. This, in turn, allows students to focus on the problem being studied. Under the concept of didactic conditions, we understand the conditions for managing the learning process. It directly refers to the content and unity of teaching, the coherence of the process, and the teacher's managerial perspective in the process. Knowledge of the didactic conditions of the creation of pedagogical situations - these are the goals and their application, sources of their construction, ways of using educational materials in the process, the tasks of different types of situations, their role in the study of the subject. rni, methods of organizing them, knowledge of methods of checking the results. When thinking about the learning situation, the external conditions that characterize the attitude towards the student are understood. These conditions stimulate the student's activity and motivate him to move faster. From a psychological point of view, a student's activity is interpreted as his or her attitude towards his or her own activities. Activity is a specific state of student coordination. It is an expression of business acumen. Thus, the structure of the innovative activity of the teacher consists of functional components, criteria, degrees and structural components.

REFERENCES:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi to'g'risida"gi Farmoni. G'G' Harakatlar strategiyasi asosida jadal taraqqiyot va yangilanish sari. – T.: G'afur
G'ulom nomidagi nashriyot-matbaa ijodiy uyi, 2017. – 92 b.
5. Elmuratova, D. M. (2017). Theoretical basis of training future teachers to innovative professional activities. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, (1).

6. Elmuratova D. Bo'lg'usi o'qituvchilarni innovatsion kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlashning tarkibiy komponentlari Berdaq nomidagi Qoraqalpoq Davlat

Universiteti Axborotnomasi № 4 B 44-46 .Nukus 2017

7. Elmuratova D. Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchisining innovatsion faoliyatga kasbiy tayyorgarligining asosiy ko'rsatkichlari. TDPU Ilmiy Axborotnomasi, ilmiynazariy jurnal. № 1. B.63-68 Toshkent 2019

8. Elmuratova D. Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini tabiatshunoslikdan kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlashning o'ziga xos jihatlari. Tafakkur sarchashmalari. Magistrlarning ilmiy-amaliy maqolalari to'plami. B.247-249. TDPU, Toshkent 2010

9. Elmuratova D. Problemo' podgotovki budihix uchiteley nachalnoga obrazovaniya k professionalnoy deyatelnosti. Inntegratsiya nauki i praktiki v sovremenno'x usloviyax materialo' VIII Mejdunaronoy konferentsii. Str 91-93 Moskva 2017

10. Elmuratova D. Talabalarda kreativlikni rivojlantirish yo'llari. Biologiya fanining dolzarb muammolari va uni o'qitishda innovatsion texnologiyalar ilmiyamaliy anjuman materiallari to'plami .B 138-141. TDPU. Toshkent 2017